

PROOF OF THE DEPASCALISATION THEOREM

Amarnath Murthy, S.E.(E&T), WLS, Oil and Natural Gas Corporation Ltd.,
Sabarmati, Ahmedabad,-380005 INDIA.

In [1] we have defined Pascalisation as follows:

Let $b_1, b_2, \dots$ be a base sequence. Then the **Smarandache Pascal derived sequence**

$d_1, d_2, \dots$ is defined as

$$d_1 = b_1$$

$$d_2 = b_1 + b_2$$

$$d_3 = b_1 + 2b_2 + b_3$$

$$d_4 = b_1 + 3b_2 + 3b_3 + b_4$$

...

$$d_{n+1} = \sum_{k=0}^n {}^n C_k \cdot b_{k+1}$$

Now Given S_d the task ahead is to find out the base sequence S_b . We call the process of extracting the base sequence from the Pascal derived sequence as **Depascalisation**. The interesting observation is that this again involves the Pascal's triangle, but with a difference.

On expressing b_k 's in terms of d_k 's We get

$$b_1 = d_1$$

$$b_2 = -d_1 + d_2$$

$$b_3 = d_1 - 2d_2 + d_3$$

$$b_4 = -d_1 + 3d_2 - 3d_3 + d_4$$

...

which suggests the possibility of

$$b_{n+1} = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n+k} \cdot {}^n C_k \cdot d_{k+1}$$

This I call as Depascalisation Theorem.

PROOF: We shall prove it by induction.

Let the proposition be true for all the numbers $l \leq k+1$. Then we have

$$b_{k+1} = {}^k C_0 (-1)^{k+2} d_1 + {}^k C_1 (-1)^{k+1} d_2 + \dots + {}^k C_k (-1)^2$$

Also we have

$$d_{k+2} = {}^{k+1} C_0 b_1 + {}^{k+1} C_1 b_2 + \dots + {}^{k+1} C_r b_{r+1} + \dots + {}^{k+1} C_{k+1} b_{k+2}, \text{ which gives}$$

$$b_{k+2} = (-1)^{k+1} C_0 b_1 - {}^{k+1} C_1 b_2 - \dots - {}^{k+1} C_r b_{r+1} - \dots + d_{k+2}$$

substituting the values of $b_1, b_2, \dots$ etc. in terms of $d_1, d_2, \dots$, we get the

coefficient of d_1 as

$$(-1)^{k+1} C_0 + (-1)^{k+1} C_1 (-1 C_0) + (-1)^{k+1} C_2 ({}^2 C_0) + \dots + (-1)^r \cdot {}^{k+1} C_r ({}^r C_0) + \dots + (-1)^{k+1} ({}^{k+1} C_k) ({}^k C_0)$$

$$- {}^{k+1} C_0 + {}^{k+1} C_1 \cdot {}^1 C_0 - {}^{k+1} C_2 \cdot {}^2 C_0 + \dots + (-1)^r \cdot {}^{k+1} C_r \cdot {}^r C_0 + \dots + (-1)^{k+1} \cdot {}^{k+1} C_k \cdot {}^k C_0$$

similarly the coefficient of d_2 is

$${}^{k+1} C_1 \cdot {}^1 C_1 + {}^{k+1} C_2 \cdot {}^2 C_1 + \dots + (-1)^{r+1} \cdot {}^{k+1} C_r \cdot {}^r C_1 + \dots + (-1)^{k+1} \cdot {}^{k+1} C_k \cdot {}^k C_1$$

on similar lines we get the coefficient of d_{m+1} as

$$\begin{aligned}
& {}^{k+1}C_m \cdot {}^mC_m + {}^{k+1}C_{m+1} \cdot {}^{m+1}C_m - \dots + (-1)^{r+m} \cdot {}^{k+1}C_{r+m} \cdot {}^{r+m}C_m + \dots + (-1)^{k+m} \cdot {}^{k+1}C_k \cdot {}^kC_m \\
= & \sum_{h=0}^{k-m} (-1)^{h+1} {}^{k+1}C_{m+h} \cdot {}^{m+h}C_m
\end{aligned}$$

$$\sum_{h=0}^{(k+1)-m} (-1)^{h+1} {}^{k+1}C_{m+h} \cdot {}^{m+h}C_m \quad \therefore \quad (-1)^{k+m} \cdot {}^{k+1}C_{k+1} \cdot {}^{k+1}C_m \quad (1)$$

Applying theorem {4.2} of reference [2], in (1) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& = {}^{k+1}C_m \{ 1 + (-1) \}^{k+1-m} + (-1)^{k+m} \cdot {}^{k+1}C_m \\
& = (-1)^{k+m} \cdot {}^{k+1}C_m
\end{aligned}$$

which shows that the proposition is true for (k+2) as well. The proposition has already been verified for k+1 = 3, hence by induction the proof is complete.

In matrix notation if we write

$$[b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n]_{1 \times n} * [p_{ij}]'_{n \times n} = [d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n]_{1 \times n}$$

where $[p_{ij}]'_{n \times n}$ = the transpose of $[p_{ij}]_{n \times n}$ and

$$[p_{ij}]_{n \times n} \text{ is given by } p_{ij} = {}^{i-1}C_{j-1} \text{ if } i \leq j \quad \text{else } p_{ij} = 0$$

Then we get the following result

If $[q_{ij}]_{n \times n}$ is the transpose of the inverse of $[p_{ij}]_{n \times n}$ Then

$$q_{ij} = (-1)^{j+i} \cdot {}^{i-1}C_{j-1}$$

We also have

$$[b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n] * [q_{ij}]'_{n \times n} = [d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n]$$

where $[q_{ij}]'_{n \times n}$ = The Transpose of $[q_{ij}]_{n \times n}$

References:

- [1] Amarnath Murthy, ' Smarandache Pascal Derived Sequences', SNJ, March ,2000.
- [2] Amarnath Murthy, 'More Results and Applications of the Smarandache Star Function., SNJ, VOL.11, No. 1-2-3, 2000.